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Article

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Gendered Differentiation in the Laws of Manu : An Analysis of Patriarchal Objectification of Women

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Abstract

In the present study of one of the Hindu Dharmasastras, the laws of Manu, we find many slokas which define the characteristics and features of proprietorship of women. Here, I try to analyse some of the notions of Manu on women. The analysis, anyhow, is not exhaustive and so very limited in its scope. Though there are various works that seek to understand Manusmriti in the context of different traditions, here I have attempted to understand Manu from the feminist standpoint.

Keywords

Law of Manu, women, patriarchy, Hinduism, gender, proprietorship

I

It is to be noted in the outset that all of the world's major/institutionalised religious traditions have always recognized the fundamental distinction between genders as being marked by the internal dialectic of male patriarchal dominance and complete female subordination and debasement. Islam, Hinduism, Buddhism, Judaism, and Christianity have understood all women, according to the context, as being essentially sick, twisted, evil creatures in need of superior masculine guidance. Here in this article, I have attempted to analyse as to how the laws of Manu erects a patriarchal social structure in its expositions, from the feminist positioning.

The German philosopher, Nietzsche, said about Manu's work that, "To set up a law book of the kind of Manu means to concede to a people the right